

removed and their reproductive rate was assessed indirectly by counting the emerging nymphs from plants that received different insecticides. The counted nymphs were removed every day, and counting went on until all eggs hatched.

The number of nymphs hatching was the criterion for evaluation of the resurgence potential of the insecticides. The number of nymphs differed significantly among treatments (see figure). The highest number emerged from plants sprayed 3 times with decamethrin. The last insecticide sprayed generally had a decisive role in inducing

or preventing BPH resurgence. In treatments where plants were sprayed twice with Perthane and then by decamethrin or methyl parathion the level of BPH resurgence was equal to that where plants were sprayed three times with methyl parathion. When Perthane was sprayed last, the number of BPH nymphs did not increase, regardless of the insecticides used in previous sprayings. This implied that even if resurgence-causing insecticide had inadvertently been used, the population buildup could be controlled by use of an insecticide that would negate the resurgence effect. ■

T. W. Mew, IRRI pathologist, on a September 1979 visit to the institute, suggested that the disease might be caused by *Erwinia* sp. S. Devadath from the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, examined the crop on 31 October and suggested that the disease might be bacterial foot rot caused by *Erwinia chrysanthemi*, which was reported by Goto in Japan in 1979. This may be the first report of the disease in India. The disease is being further investigated. ■

A new record of rice transitory yellowing virus in northern Thailand

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Yellowing symptoms of rice plants similar to those of rice transitory yellowing disease (RTYV) occurred on wet-season rice at the late growth stage in August–September 1979 in Chiengrai and Chiengmai, northern Thailand. At locations where disease symptoms were observed, 18 to 32% of the hills were infested.

Electromicroscopic observations of dip preparations and ultrathin sections of diseased plants revealed that bullet-shaped virus particles (90 x 120 nm in dip preparations, 90 x 180 nm in ultrathin sections) were similar to those found in diseased leaves infected with RTYV in Taiwan and Okinawa, Japan. In ultrathin sections, the virus particles were observed in phloem cells of diseased plants. *Nephotettix nigropictus* and *N. cincticeps* transmitted the virus effectively and in a persistent manner. The virus incubation period in the insects was about 2 weeks; the viruliferous insects often remained infective during their entire life span.

The virus belonging to the rhabdovirus group was identified as rice transitory

The influence of insecticide used in spray sequence on brown planthopper reproductive rate. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University and IRRI.

A new bacterial disease of rice

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Most plants in a 2-ha plot of the variety Pankaj were observed to be drying during a routine field visit to the Institute farm in 1979 kharif. The crop was in the maximum-tillering stage. The growth of the infected plants was somewhat stunted. From a distance the disease appeared to

be the kresak stage of bacterial blight. But a closer examination showed black and rotting basal internodes and enclosing leaf sheaths. The gummy, rotted portion emitted a foul odor. Core portions of tillers dried first; sometimes the central leaf dried much earlier than the other leaves and the symptoms resembled those of stem borer damage. The dried leaves were erect and straw color. Only a few tillers in most infected hills remained healthy. Roots were normal but dried tillers could easily be pulled out.